

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Substituted Diaroylmethane/Acrylophenone Complexes of Copper(II)

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Complexation behaviour of unsymmetrically substituted diaroylmethanes/arylophenones (β -diketones) towards copper(II) has been studied. The complexes were characterised on the basis of analytical, magnetic, ir, nmr and electronic spectral data. Most of the compounds exhibited good antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

β -DIKETONES have been found to possess various biological activities¹. Some methoxy- and hydroxy- β -diketones are of pharmaceutical² importance. Some naphthyl and phenanthryl compounds exhibit potent bacteriocidal and carcinogenic³ activity. The *o*-hydroxy- β -diketones are good chelating agents used for determination of metal ions⁴. The present paper describes the synthesis of various substituted diaroylmethane/acrylophenone (HL) complexes with Cu^{II} and study of their biological activity.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. The ligands diaroylmethanes were synthesised by Bekar-Venkataraman transformation⁵ of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones. The substituted acrylophenones were prepared by condensation of various substituted aromatic aldehydes in the presence of base⁷. The purity of the ligands was checked from their m.ps.

Cu^{II} complexes: Aqueous solution of copper sulphate and ethanolic solution of substituted diaroylmethane (for 1-4)/acrylophenone (for 5-16; Table 1) were mixed in the 1:2 molar ratio and dilute ammonium hydroxide was added till yellow coloured complexes precipitates out (pH > 4.5). The complexes were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried (Table 1).

The complexes were characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis, magnetic moment (at room temperature), uv, ir (KBr) and pmr spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis data correspond to 1:2 metal-ligand stoichiometry for the complexes. All the complexes are stable at room temperature and are insoluble in common organic solvents. Magnetic

moment values of the Cu^{II} complexes have been found to lie in the usual range 1.69-1.75 B.M.

Due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding in *o*-hydroxy aromatic aldehydes and ketones, ν_{C-OH} band is generally observed⁸ at 3410 cm⁻¹. This band is absent in the ir spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes. The coordination of the oxygen of the hydroxy group is confirmed by the lowering of ν_{C-O} from 1090-1115 to 1040-1055 cm⁻¹. Two sharp and strong bands assigned for $\nu_{C=O}$ at 1680 and 1660 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand, are lowered by 60-70 cm⁻¹ on complexation thus indicating the coordination from the oxygen of the carbonyl group. All the complexes showed a band⁹ at 390-410 cm⁻¹ (Cu-O). In the free ligand the ν_{C-O} (phenolic) band is observed at 1282 cm⁻¹; on complexation with the metals this band shifted to higher energy by about 40-60 cm⁻¹ indicating phenolic oxygen coordination of the acrylophenone.

Electronic spectra of the complexes showed absorption maxima at 29410, 23520 and 20618 cm⁻¹. The strong absorption¹⁰ at 29410 cm⁻¹ is expected to be due to ligand-Cu^{II} charge transfer. Two bands observed at 23520 and 20618 cm⁻¹ were assigned to ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transition¹¹.

In the ¹H nmr spectra, the signals due to aromatic CH₃ were observed as singlet at δ 2.3. The resonance signal due to methylene of diaroylmethane complexes (1-4) was observed at δ 2.6. The aromatic protons exhibited the multiplet at δ 6.8-7.5. The signal due to OH (phenolic) was found to be disappeared because of the complexation with metal.

Biological screening: All the complexes were tested for their antibacterial activity by agar-diffusion technique¹² using dimethyl formamide as solvent against *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve) bacteria at 25 and 50 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration. The tetracycline was used as standard. The complexes revealed moderate

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Compd. $\text{Cu(L)}_2\text{SO}_4$	Groups								M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X ₄	Y ₄	Y ₅	Y ₆	Cu		N	OI	
1	$[\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	Cl	—	—	—	250	8.50 (8.65)	—	9.60 (9.66)	
2	$[\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	—	—	—	300d	8.41 (8.30)	5.70 (5.60)	—	
3	$[\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	H	OH ₂	NO ₂	—	—	—	291d	8.41 (8.30)	5.70 (5.60)	—	
4	$[\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	NO ₂	OH ₂	H	Cl	—	—	—	360d	7.45 (7.70)	3.30 (3.39)	8.52 (8.61)	
5	$[\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	NO ₂	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H	NO ₂	220	5.60 (5.72)	7.45 (7.58)	—	
6	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	OH ₂	OH	300d	6.95 (7.08)	3.00 (3.12)	—	
7	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	H	OH ₂	NO ₂	H	H	OH	250d	6.48 (6.69)	1.40 (1.47)	—	
8	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H	OH ₂	301d	6.50 (6.60)	2.80 (2.91)	—	
9	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{10}\text{Cl}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	Cl	H	OCH ₂	OH	240d	6.25 (6.33)	—	6.95 (7.08)	
10	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	NO ₂	OH ₂	H	Cl	H	OCH ₂	OH	276d	5.75 (5.81)	2.45 (2.56)	6.38 (6.49)	
11	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	NO ₂	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	OCH ₂	OH	298	5.60 (5.70)	4.90 (5.02)	—	
12	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H	OCH ₂	312	6.25 (6.40)	2.70 (2.82)	—	
13	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	OH	H	>300d	6.40 (6.59)	6.40 (6.59)	—	
14	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	Cl	H	H	OH	200d	6.60 (6.72)	—	7.40 (7.53)	
15	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	NO ₂	OH ₂	H	Cl	H	OH	H	265	6.00 (6.15)	2.60 (2.71)	6.70 (6.87)	
16	$[\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cu}]\text{SO}_4$	H	OH ₂	H	H	H	H	NO ₂	270d	6.70 (6.82)	2.90 (3.00)	—	

*d=decomposed.

sensitivity against gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria. The metal complexes of β-diketones are

more potent than pure ligands. In general, the complexes showed significant antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* than *S. aureus*. The probable correlation of structure and activity can be established and that the presence of halogen as well as nitro group in the ligand moiety enhances the antibacterial activity.

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References

1. P. F. DEVITT, A. TIMONEY and M. A. VICKARS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **28**, 4941; N. P. BUU-HOI and N. D. XUONG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 39; S. S. MISHRA and R. S. TEWARI, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1972, **35**, 95; S. S. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 68; S. C. KUSHAWAHA, DINAKAR and J. B. LAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 82.
2. G. W. WILSON and D. E. LLOYD, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1949, **95**, 399.
3. M. KAMODA, *J. Agric. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1954, **28**, 791.
4. K. SVAMASUNDAR, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1964, **60**, 259, 1968, **67**, 90; R. R. NAIDU *Curr. Sci.*, 1968, **37**, 342.
5. R. R. NAIDU, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 615.
6. W. BAKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1381; K. VENKATARAMAN and H. S. MAHAL, *Curr. Sci.*, 1933, **2**, 214.
7. M. B. HOGALE, B. N. PAWAR, A. R. SHELAR and B. P. NIKAM, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 1987, **3**, 57.
8. L. J. BELLAMY, "The IR Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1964, p. 95.
9. N. THAKARAJAN and K. KRISHNAMURTHY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 401.
10. G. A. AGAMBER and K. G. ORREL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 897.
11. R. S. NAIDU and R. R. NAIDU, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 1625.
12. M. M. NANDI and A. K. MISHRA, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1981, **44**, 19.